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How to Teach Teenagers with Deviant Behavior to Express Their Thoughts and Feelings?

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Abstract

The relevance of the issue arises from the need to present experimental data confirming significance of the realization of educational potential of world literature in forming communicative skills of adolescents with deviant behavior. The purpose of this study is to uncover the scope of Humanities (primarily philological) in the process of addressing the realization of the creative potential of adolescents with deviant behavior in order to shape their moral values, create a positive learning and life motivation, and teach them to express their feelings and thoughts. The article consists of three parts. The first part of the article gives the theoretical basis of the development of communication skills among adolescents with deviant behavior. The second part of the article includes the research. The study involved 247 adolescents from two Kazan schools. As diagnostic tools, we have chosen the following diagnostics: 1) a diagnostic technique for deviating behavior (two options for girls and boys, respectively) by A.N. Orel; 2) the Cook and Medley Hostility Scale; 3) the Spielberger-Hanin Test. In the second stage, extracurricular activities were conducted with the experimental group for several months in order to carry out prevention using various activities and games, psychogymnastic exercises and trainings, and also to correct and reduce levels of aggression, anxiety, shyness, to correct the level of self-esteem among adolescents of the experimental group. In addition, in the experimental group, special trainings were held aimed at the formation of skills to properly express their thoughts. One of the types of work in this direction was the study of the haiku poetic genre unusual for Russian students. The third part of this article presents the analysis of the study and its conclusion. Haiku contributes to the realization of a strong emotional outburst; in addition, it is a good way to show how a person perceives the world around. The work on composing haiku with adolescents with deviant behavior helps go beyond self-analysis, personal concerns, and focuses on the outside world. The effectiveness of the program is verified and proven using the Wilcoxon T-test.

Keywords: teenagers with deviant behavior; educational potential; experimental haiku (hokku); cyberbullying.

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Introduction

People who grew up at the beginning of the 21st century understand that they live in a different world. The world in which we grew up is significantly different from the one in which modern children live. And the challenges that adults faced in their adolescence are radically different from those that modern adolescents experience.

The real threat for modern children is an increasing level of violence in its most diverse forms. Unfortunately, shooting of classmates, beating of peers and teachers, knife attacks and other violent incidents, recently specific for North American educational establishments, nowadays occur in Russian schools. This threat for schoolchildren and their parents has become so major that bulletproof backpacks go on sale.

Despite transformation of surrounding environment, teaching activity is still unique in many aspects. Sometimes it is a skill; sometimes it is everyday social work that combines creativity and morality. There can be little debate among Russian teachers, especially those who work with teenagers with deviant behavior, that teaching is social.

Deviant behavior (we will use this concept) is behavior that does not conform to generally accepted social or cultural norms. It is sometimes viewed as a synonym for the notion of abnormal behavior. The deviant behavior is unacceptable behavior or action that is unorthodox for social and cultural norms, that is, behavior or actions viewed through the prism of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation. A person with deviant behavior deviates from what is acceptable in society. For example, murder is a form of extreme manifestation of deviant behavior, violating the law and the cultural norm, which states that you cannot kill another person. By the way, intimidation or disobedience is also a manifestation of behavior that deviates from the norm. However, there is no punishment for these misdeeds in the Criminal Law.

The first step in understanding the deviant behavior is to study cultural and social norms. Norms vary in different cultures, and it happens that behavior that is acceptable in one culture can be considered rude or out of place in the other. But the evolution of society, and as a consequence, the evolution of norms allows one to transform this concept and its content over time. For example, wearing gloves in public was once the social norm for ladies in many Western countries, but now such a lady is considered slightly eccentric (unless the weather is cold).

“According to the APA Dictionary of Psychology (VandenBos, 2007), deviance is defined as “any behavior that deviates significantly from what is considered appropriate or typical for a social group” ...” (Sanches, Gouveia-Pereira, Marôco, Gomes, & Roncon, 2016).

The origin of deviant behavior in pedagogy is usually considered from three perspectives: psychological, biological, and sociological.

Alternatively, sociologists consider the social status of a violator of social norms and give an example: stealing is a general case of deviant behavior which is caused by sociological pressure, for example, such as poverty. However, it is not uncommon for theft to be made by well-off people who do not suffer from a lack of prosperity.

Biologists explain deviant behavior of organic brain lesions that lead to manifestations of deviation, as well as biological motives for normal behavior.

Psychologists are interested in thinking processes that underlie normal and deviant behavior, including depression, which can cause a person to commit acts that do not conform to generally accepted

norms. Besides, together with teachers, psychologists try to study the early childhood of offenders, since a person learns about acceptable behavioral boundaries in his or her early childhood.

Most scientists agree that there is no single explanation for the origin of deviant behavior, but they recognize a multifactor approach to its study, i.e. explain the emergence of deviant behavior due to the influence of many factors.

There are a lot of studies focused on deviant behavior, and the problem of adolescents with deviant behavior is the nature of inter-branch interaction of social institutions.

Law enforcement authorities, teachers, psychologists, educational psychologists, social and rehabilitation centers, centers for complementary education and healthcare institutions focus on the aforementioned category of children.

After analyzing the methods of working with adolescents with deviant behavior, it can be noted that a considerable emphasis is placed on communicative abilities of such children. Then there are studies on rehabilitation and socialization of teenagers with deviant behavior. There are works focused on the influence of family of a teenager on his/her deviant behavior. Numerous works deal with prevention of deviant behavior both within educational institutions and centers for complementary education and sports schools. Individual ways of development that can promote “positive psychological and pedagogical support for teenagers and initiation of health projects to maintain social and psychological balance of personality” are being elaborated (Zinnurov, 2013).

The works of Gerbeev, Groisman, Kostyashkin, Medvedev, Nevsky and others were dedicated to the analysis of social and pedagogical causes of behavior deviations of minors; the psychological specifics of deviant behavior was investigated by Alekseyev, Alemaskin, Badmaev, Belicheva, Kovalev, Slavina, Feldstein and others; the legal aspects of the problem was studied by Almazov, Dolgovoy, Ermakov, Minkovsky and others; the development of diagnostics of deviations in behavior of minors can be found in works of Belkin, Obukhov, Stepanov and others; Akhiyarov, Girfanova, Gurov, Zinnurov, Nevsky, Novik, Ostrovsky, Sviridov, Yurichka and others paid their attention to search for ways and means of preventing and overcoming deviant behavior of students.

Foreign scientists such as Baron, Park, Dollard, Bandura, Richardson, Dilts, Lorenz, Skinner, Torndike, Mid, Rogers, Maslow, Parsons and others worked on problems of overcoming and preventing various manifestations of deviant behavior.

In the last decade, there have appeared studies of teachers and psychologists concerning the training of psychologists for working with deviants (Barkaeva, 2009), religious addiction prevention and protection against influence on teenagers (Gorokhov, 2018), prevention of deviant behavior from the perspective of learning environment (Akhmetkhanov, 2015), peculiarities of experiencing psychological problems by deviant adolescents (Belobrykin, 2017), cybercrime problems and low self-esteem (Donner, Markus, Jennings, Higgins, Banfield), etc.

However, experience shows that the use of new programs of work with adolescents who demonstrate antisocial behavior is often fragmented, as a set of unrelated episodic events implemented by different departments, which does not provide, in our opinion, the necessary systemic effect for preventing socially negative phenomena in youth environment. Therefore, this problem in modern Russian society is still acute and urgent. It requires searching for more effective measures both from government and public organizations.

The task of overcoming deviant behavior of young generation in its various forms requires a deep understanding of its causes. According to experts, causes of deviant behavior are social inequality; loss of

spiritual and moral values; social indifference to the fate of children caught up in a difficult life situation; unfavorable environment of upbringing in the family; school disadaptation of adolescents; influence of criminogenic factors; mental deviations, etc. We would add here the underestimation of empathy and the communicative-forming component in the organized educational and correctional work with troubled children.

In adolescence, compared with youth age, the use of constructions relating to interpersonal interaction is much more common. Such constructions as “community of interests”, “I can trust”, “they understand me”, “devotion”, and “ability to help” are typical for adolescents.

Observations show that emotional experiences of individual psychological problems of deviant adolescents differ from those peculiar to their peers with socially acceptable behavior (Belobrykina & Limonchenko, 2017).

In other words, in adolescence characteristics of another person which determine the possibility of establishing trustworthy and close friendly relations play a key role. Individuality in adolescence is mostly understood in global terms, which are used in various spheres including interpersonal communications. Properties referring to the worldview, creativity, cognition (such as a talent, enthusiasm) are becoming more and more significant. This coincides with data on the increase during adolescence, the number of used nonsituative personal characteristics (Shtil'shtein, 2000).

Another danger for teenagers – totalitarian sects and radical religious establishment – has appeared recently. “The main prevention of religious and human influence dependence should be development of own opinions based on education and acquisition of fundamental knowledge on religion bases and traditional religions. It is especially significant to start informational and preventive work at school age. Knowledge of the features of religious behavior and symptoms of religious addiction is important as this is expected to contribute to prevention and prompt detection of unlawful conduct among youth (Gorokhova, 2018)”.

Representatives of law enforcement bodies state that the amount of teenagers coming unlawful actions decreases every year. The amount of children affected by unlawful actions of teenagers with deviant behavior is increasing. Activities of law enforcement officers are limited by detecting a violator and punishing the violator. How to bring a trespasser back to ordinary life? Or another important problem: what to do with a child in relation to the violation of social norms? How to rehabilitate him/her?

Another problem concerns children who commit acts that go beyond the norm, but have not yet become the subjects of close monitoring by law enforcement agencies, that is, actions and behavior of children, which do not fall within the scope of criminal law. This now includes the so-called “trolling” in social networks, cyberbullying, etc. There is a “victim” in the peer group, against which a social network group is created. In this group, photographs of the “victim” and degrading comments are posted. Peers are encouraged to make angry and threatening comments on the child’s wall. Photos of the “victim” are distorted with the help of Photoshop and memes are generated on their basis. Cyberbullying is a serious problem for many teenagers. From the point of view of an aggressor, this form of persecution of other children does not entail any risk for him or her, since it can be carried out anonymously and at a distance and the aggressor can escape the consequences in the form of punishment.

To teach a teenager to respond to bullying and intimidation not only in social networks and cyberspace but in everyday communication with peers is a relevant task for teachers and psychologists. Successful communication allows minimizing such risks for teenagers as aggressive behavior, physical and psychological violence, anxiety and other manifestations specific for deviant behavior.

In this paper, we concentrate on the issue: how to teach teenagers with deviant behavior to express their thoughts and feelings.

Methodology

Pupils of eighth and ninth grades from two Kazan schools took part in the research. The consent was signed by their parents or legal representatives. Each school has got 4 classes. 213 schoolchildren from the first school comprised an experimental group, and 214 schoolchildren from the second school were in a screening group. The research involved 427 pupils: 203 girls and 224 boys. First of all, we diagnosed teenagers to figure out whether their behavior was deviant or not. Diagnostics of deviant behavior in early childhood is important to help a child correct his or her behavior.

Some scholars consider provoking and deviant behavior as synonymous. Hence, they use the same definition.

There are two ways to diagnose defiant behavior: 1) a respondent answers the questions on his/her own about persuasion; 2) researchers determine the respondent's self-esteem.

The first way, in our opinion, is less reliable, as memory, bias and stealth can affect the answers. As for the second way, teenagers with deviant behavior have either too high or very low self-esteem. In other words, this way does not show the self-esteem measurement result.

We have chosen the following diagnostic tools: 1) diagnostic techniques of deviant behavior (two options, for girls and boys); 2) Cook and Medley Hostility Scale; 3) The Spielberg-Hanin tests of anxiety.

The first diagnosis of propensity for deviant behavior is a standardized questionnaire test which includes a set of specialized psychodiagnostic scales (informative and official) focused on a measurement tendency to realize some forms of deviant behavior. This methodology contains questions for girls (98 statement questions) and boys (89 statement questions).

The second diagnosis (Cook and Medley Hostility Scale) identifies such clear symptoms of deviant behavior as cynicism, aggression and hostility.

The selection of the third diagnosis can be attributed to the fact that teenagers with deviant behavior show a high level of anxiety. Therefore, we used the Spielberg-Hanin test of anxiety to determine their anxiety level. This method made it possible to reliably determine the level of anxiety at the exact moment of time (anxiety state as a condition) and a side of one's character. The method of measuring anxiety both as a personal trait and a state was worked out by Spielberger and adapted in Russian by Hanin.

Having undertaken the first diagnostics and evaluated the answers on seven scales, we learned that there were 48 teenagers with deviant behavior from the first school (22.5% of total participants), 44 boys and 4 girls, and 49 teenagers (22.9% of total participants), 45 boys and 4 girls from the second school. Our experimental groups were confirmed during the survey with teachers and by youth liaison officers. We have received almost similar groups in relation to quantity and age. The experimental group consisted of 48 persons, and the control group consisted of 49 persons.

Based on the second diagnostics results, we obtained the following data: cynicism, aggressiveness and hostility prevail among teenagers.

On the cynicism scale in the experimental group of adolescents with a high level: 16 people (33.3%), 22 people (45.9%) with an average indicator with a tendency to high, 10 pupils (20.8%) with an average indicator with a tendency to low, with a low level - not detected (0%).

On the aggressiveness scale of adolescents with a high level: 13 pupils (27%), 24 people (50%)

with an average indicator with a tendency to high, 11 pupils (23%) were identified with an average indicator with a tendency to low, and a low level was not revealed (0%). On the hostility scale of adolescents with a high level: 12 people (25%), 20 schoolchildren (41.7%) with an average indicator with a tendency to high, 16 pupils (33.3%) with an average indicator with a tendency to low, with a low level (0%).

In the control group on the cynicism scale of adolescents with a high level: 30 people (61.2%), 19 people (38.8%) with an average indicator with a tendency to high, students with an average score with a tendency to low and a low indicator (0%).

On the aggressiveness scale of adolescents with a high indicator: 28 pupils (57.1%), 13 people (26.5%) with an average indicator with a tendency to high, 8 pupils (16.4%) with an average indicator with a tendency to low, a low indicator was not revealed (0%).

On the scale of hostility of adolescents with a high level: 20 people (40.8%), 23 schoolchildren (47%) with an average indicator with a tendency to high, 6 pupils (12.2%) with an average indicator with a tendency to low, and a low level was also not detected (0%).

At the next stage of the study, situational and personal anxiety was determined. The adolescents answered 40 questions, 20 for each of the scales.

The final result showed that 14 pupils (29.2%) in the experimental group and 11 pupils (22.5%) from the control group had a very high level of situational anxiety. Considerable anxiety, tension and nervousness are characteristic for these teenagers. This causes a disturbance of attention and sometimes an impaired fine motor coordination.

16 students (33.3%) in the experimental group and 14 in the control group (28.6%) experienced a high level of situational anxiety. Nervousness was also common for them.

The average level of situational anxiety was demonstrated by 10 people (20.8%) in the experimental group and 12 students (24.5%) from the control group.

8 adolescents (16.7%) from the experimental group and 11 in the control group (22.45%) had a low level of anxiety.

Only one pupil (2%) from the control group had a very low level of situational anxiety. In the experimental group, there were no such teenagers.

On the scale of personal anxiety, 12 pupils (25%) in the experimental group and 13 pupils (26.5%) from the control group had a very high level of anxiety.

A high level of personal anxiety was detected in 15 students (31.2%) in the experimental group and 16 students (32.65%) in the control group. For these teenagers, anxiety and nervousness are also common.

The average level of situational anxiety was demonstrated by 7 people (14.6%) in the experimental group and 12 students (24.5%) from the control group.

A low level of anxiety was found in 13 adolescents (27.1%) in the experimental group and 6 in the control group (12.25%).

Only one pupil (2.1%) from the experimental group and two children (4.1%) from the control group demonstrated a very low level of situational anxiety. In the experimental group, there were no such teenagers.

Personal anxiety characterizes a strong tendency to perceive many situations as threatening and respond to them with anxiety.

We consider it important to note the need to pay attention not only to students who demonstrate a

high and a very high level of anxiety, but also to adolescents with “excessive calmness” (with a very low level of anxiety). Such insensitivity is, as a rule, protective and hinders a full formation of the individuality.

Based on the results of the initial study, we developed a plan of special event to implement preventive measures with the help of various activities and various games, psycho-gymnastic exercises and training. These events are intended to correct and reduce the level of aggression, anxiety, shyness, and adjust the level of self-esteem in adolescents from the experimental group. Special measures were not implemented with adolescents from the control group.

In addition to a special program for correcting deviant behavior in the experimental group, the adolescents underwent special training. This training was designed to develop skills of correctly expressing their thoughts.

One type of work in this direction was a non-traditional Russian poetic genre - hokku.

Through an ordinary survey we found out that the children are not familiar with this genre of Japanese poetry (“what is this?”, “I hear about it for the first time”). The literature curriculum (edited by Korovin and Marantzman) includes the study of hokku in the 7th grade. Anyone who wants to express his/her thoughts, feelings in the original three-line form, can try his/her hand at creating hokku. It is noted by teachers and curriculum developers that hokku helps develop fresh thinking. Hokku is also found helpful in psychotherapy: a person can be described by a hokku that he/she writes (Zinnurov, 2013).

Results

The research participants were teenagers at the age of 14, but younger than 18. The correction of impact on adolescents, whose personality has not yet been fully formed, who are mentally and socially immature is primarily an educational task. Hence, we suggested such teenagers get acquainted with the “Nine haiku from the prison for juvenile criminals in Helby” (written by Tranströmer, translated by Kudryavitsky). A detailed description of the lesson on this topic was published by us earlier (Novik, 2011).

After studying the biography of the author, the Nobel Prize winner in literature in 2011, the Swedish poet Tomas Tranströmer, known in Russia as a creator of experimental haiku (hokku), we use a certain educational resource for conversation with adolescents with deviant behavior. Holding a degree in psychology, Tomas Tranströmer worked with juvenile criminals, and then with people who were seriously injured at the workplace (Potemkin, 2001). A curious fact for students: the Swedes themselves note that Tranströmer has very good poems. He has tragic poems, but mostly it is the tragedy that happened to him. The most important thing is that his poetry is without smugness.

Discussions

In the process of working with children with deviant behavior, we suggest teenagers read these hokkus, share their feelings, choose one of the nine hokkus and explain their preference. It is appreciated if a teacher will tell about his/her choice, share his/her feelings, experiences after reading.

1. Confusion

during a game of football:
the ball flew over the wall.

2. They make a noise
scare the time

make it go faster

3. Life with opaque
beauty is here -
pictures on tattoos

4. Caught fugitive
empties pockets
full of chanterelles

5. Noise of works,
watchtower
surprise forest

6. The grate is raised
enter the courtyard
in another season

7. The lamp illuminates the wall
midges see stain
unreal light

8. A truck is passing at night
dreams of prisoners
tremble

9. Having drunk milk
the guy falls asleep
the camera is a stone mother.

Since this category of children is just learning a new genre of poetry and does not have necessary skills of writing, first we suggest the teenagers draw the hokku of Tranströmer and then compose poems by themselves. If a child cannot compose a hokku, a teacher may help and support him/her and later show the work to other children highlighting positive aspects. We have discussed the drawings taking into account authors' comments (an author explained what he/she wanted to show, what he/she felt while drawing). In most cases, the pictures and answers of adolescents are primitive. For example, "I painted a tattoo (Hokku No. 3). I know what tattoos are on my father's body and what they mean. I'll get the same tattoo. I heard that it hurts and you can get infected by various diseases, but I don't care ...", or "I drew a soccer ball (Hokku No. 1), I cannot draw people. What do I feel? I do not feel anything. I want to play football, but my leg hurts - I had a fight yesterday....", "I drew a bar (Hokku No. 6). I feel sorry for those who are locked up....". Hokku, created by teenagers with deviant behavior, are presented below.

On the example of this genre, we tried to explain to adolescents with deviant behavior what psychological analysis in the literature is. In an accessible way, we tried to describe that it is an image of a

person's mental life. The forms of psychological analysis are diverse: from direct author's explanations to "internal" monologues of heroes. Open forms of explanation of the psychology of heroes are called "explicit psychologism", hidden forms (for example, by indicating changes in the appearance of the character) – "secret psychology". A landscape, interior, artistic details can also acquire an additional psychological meaning.

Firstly, the children in the experimental group tried to find (with the help of questions) these artistic elements in hokku. And later they identified them without a clue. After a surge of emotion in creative work, students need self-expression and try to compose hokku outside of training sessions.

The next stage was independent writing of hokkus, with the help of a teacher if there was a need. Below are some original hokkus composed by the participants:

Mom says I'm selfish
She doesn't know me at all.
I do not know her either.

Forgive me, mom.
I just now realized:
In the eyes to look at all is not terrible

Should adults teach to love?
Who said this?
I myself can teach them love.

I know that when I leave school,
I won't consider myself to be an abandoned person.
Here is my family.

There are people around me, cars.
And I'm on the road. One.
I'm like a spit on the asphalt.

When the work has been finished, we conducted a restudy of children in the control and experimental groups and analyzed the work efficiency results with all participants of the educational process.

We did not make the first diagnosis. It was necessary only to identify adolescents with deviant behavior. In the control and experimental groups, we evaluated the deviant behavior at the beginning of the experiment: the Cook-Medley Hostility Scale and determined the levels of anxiety with the help of the Spielberg-Hanin test.

Having diagnosed the Cook-Medley Hostility Scale again, we found that significant changes took place in the experimental group for each of the scales of cynicism.

On the scale of cynicism there were 6 people with a high rate (12.5%), 21 people (43.75%) with an average indicator with a tendency to high, 21 students (43.75%) with an average indicator with a tendency to low and a low indicator was also not revealed.

As for aggressiveness, there were 3 pupils with a high level (6.25%), 21 people (43.75%) with an average indicator with a tendency to high, 24 pupils (50%) with an average indicator with a tendency to low, with a low index not found.

On the hostility scale, there were 26 schoolchildren (54.1%) with an average indicator with a tendency to high, 22 pupils (45.9%) with an average indicator with a tendency to low, and nobody had high and low levels (0%).

The control group also experienced positive changes in some scales, but not as significant as in the experimental group.

Thus, on the cynicism scale, 25 (51%) and 24 (49%) adolescents had an average indicator with a tendency to high and a tendency to low, respectively. Nobody had high and low indicators (0%).

A high level of aggressiveness was detected in 16 pupils (32.65%). 24 schoolchildren (49%) had an average indicator with a tendency to high, 9 pupils (18.35%) - an average indicator with a tendency to low. Adolescents with a low index were not found.

A high indicator of hostility was found in 10 people (20.4%). 27 schoolchildren (55.1%) had an average indicator with a tendency to high, 12 students (24.5%) had an average indicator with a tendency to low. Adolescents with a low level of hostility were not revealed. The final stage was the determination of situational and personal anxiety. Again in the experimental group, we observed significant positive changes in the diagnosis results.

We found out that 6 people (12.5%) in the experimental group and 8 pupils (16.3%) from the control group had a very high level of situational anxiety. Increased anxiety, tension and nervousness are specific for these teenagers. A high level of state anxiety was detected in 12 pupils (25%) in the experimental group and 11 pupils (22.5%) from the control group. For these teenagers, anxiety and nervousness are also specific. The average level of situational anxiety was demonstrated by 25 people (52.1%) in the experimental group and 18 pupils (36.7%) from the control group. 5 teenagers (10.4%) in the experimental group and 11 pupils (22.5%) in the control group had a low level of anxiety. A very low level of situational anxiety was detected in only 1 pupil (2%) from the control group. There were no such teenagers in the experimental group.

7 people (14.6%) from the experimental group and 10 pupils (20.4%) from the control group had a very high level of personal anxiety. A high level of personal anxiety was detected in 10 students (20.8%) in the experimental group and 16 students (32.6%) in the control group. The average level of situational anxiety was demonstrated by 18 schoolchildren (37.5%) from the experimental group and 13 pupils (26.6%) from the control group. A low level of anxiety was experienced by 12 adolescents (25%) in the experimental group and 8 pupils (16.3%) in the control group. Only 1 pupil (2.1%) from the experimental group and two children (4.1%) from the control group had a very low level of situational anxiety. There were no such teenagers in the experimental group.

The Wilcoxon T-test was used as the main method of mathematical data processing. It helped us analyze the intervention program effectiveness. We set out to prove the effectiveness of the intervention and development program intended to reduce the level of cynicism, aggressiveness, hostility and anxiety (situational and personal) in adolescents with deviant behavior.

We used the online calculation, placed in the public domain. We entered the data obtained before and after the intervention program and received the result: $T < T_{kp}$ (0.01). Based on this result one can say with a probability of 99% that the level of decrease of cynicism, aggressiveness, hostility and anxiety (state and trait) after the intervention program is much higher than an increase of these indicators. Thus, there

was a significant decrease in the level of cynicism, aggressiveness, hostility and anxiety in adolescents who had implemented the intervention program (probability value $p < 0.01$).

The level of hostility, cynicism, aggressiveness and anxiety (situational and personal) of adolescents with deviant behavior after the prevention and development program has decreased. Therefore, it makes it possible to change the behavior of the above-mentioned category of adolescents.

Conclusion

Hokku facilitates the realization of a strong emotional outburst. In addition, it is a good way to show how a person perceives the world. Composing haikus both with future employees of law enforcement agencies and adolescents with deviant behavior helps to go beyond digging into oneself, their private troubles and concentrating on the world around them. To be happy or sad about the changes that time carries in itself is inherent in all peoples.

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